

TRANSLATION IS IMPORTANT IN THE MODERN WORLD OF COMPETENCE

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ABSTRACT

Visual memorization methods effectively increase the amount of RAM. Psychologists say that the use of mechanical memory is the most ineffective way to remember information, in contrast to logical and figurative methods of memorization. Semantic grouping is the selection of strong points that facilitate memorization. Based on the work of psychologists, translators and methodologists who have studied the problems of oral translation to some extent, we come to the conclusion that two aspects are especially important in oral translation - oral form and interaction. An interpreter translates an oral conversation or discussion into various communicative situations, where messages are exchanged between people through the interpreter.

According to R. Minyar-Beloruchev, the most effective way to develop the translator's memory is the semantic grouping of the text, including repetition, logical understanding of the material, systematization, highlighting the main logical components of information, repetition in your own words. logical repetition, figurative methods of memorization - translating information based on images, graphs, diagrams, pictures. Psychologists say that the use of mechanical memory is the most ineffective way to remember information, in contrast to logical and figurative methods of memorization. Visual memorization methods effectively increase the amount of RAM. It is a more stable form of memory that is almost impossible to erase, because it arises from a person's interests and professional knowledge and is inseparable from his personality.

Semantic grouping is the selection of strong points that facilitate memorization. In addition, in sequential interpretation, it is impossible to remember all the words in a sentence, given that all languages are redundant. Redundancy of language, especially in oral speech, is necessary for good human understanding, but for the process of consecutive translation, it often becomes an obstacle, because it overloads the working memory and complicates the process of recalling information. All of the above allows us to conclude that in order to carry out the process of consecutive translation, the translator must be able to select the words that contain the main information from the speech stream. Translation is a very

important activity in the modern world of communication. The nature of commentary imposes certain limitations, such as time pressure, changing information, and the rapid selection of suitable topics to be covered in a short period of time. Based on the work of psychologists, translators and methodologists who have studied the problems of oral translation to some extent, we come to the conclusion that two aspects are especially important in oral translation - oral form and interaction. An interpreter translates an oral conversation or discussion into various communicative situations, where messages are exchanged between people through the interpreter. According to the Austrian scientist F. Pochhacker, interpretation is a form of translation based on a one-time presentation of the original and final performance of the statement in another language. The question of how to successfully reproduce a message in another language is undoubtedly of great interest to translators. But this issue is especially difficult for translators who find themselves in various situations where the cultural, linguistic and lexical characteristics of languages can cause serious problems. Regardless of the situation, a skilled translator must ensure that the true meaning of the message is conveyed between two or more languages.

However, it is necessary not only to describe the two disciplines and define the essence of each, but to explain them in such a way that the main problems that can be faced by consecutive translators become clear. It should be noted that many people, including students studying translation, do not distinguish between the terms "translation" - "written translation" and "interpreter" - "translation" at all, and in many cases they confuse them. This leads to the misconception that any translator can be a good translator. Such a conclusion can be reached on the basis of the researcher's continuous translation experience during his professional career. Furthermore, the notion that translation and interpreting are activities inextricably linked to at least two languages and two cultural traditions contributes to the misconception that the two activities are the same. However, there is a more serious problem with translation due to the time factor, which is a significant difference between the two activities. As a result, some of the mistakes that inevitably occur cause problems in understanding and therefore lead to very weak or in some cases zero communication. D. Seleskovich emphasizes that interpretation should not be considered as the interpretation of words. What a translator has to do is to reveal the meaning and make it "clear" so that people who speak another language can understand it. The author also said, "a translation is more like a picture than a photograph. The photograph repeats the words without trying to explain their meaning. As the artist sees with his own eyes, the painting seeks to find meaning, convey a message, and reflect the object. As for consecutive translation, which is the focus of this study, the French scientist D. Gilles defines it as repeating the entire content of the message from the original speech without creating a report, conclusion, and commentary on the original speech. In this mode, translation is usually the highest form of activity, because such translation requires the completion of the comprehension phase before the formation phase begins, since most of the components of the linguistic form of the phrase are lost from memory and replaced after a few seconds. Based on the studies we have reviewed, we conclude that interpreting has evolved over time and includes different methods or types used to communicate in different settings. In addition to the two main types of interpreting, simultaneous and consecutive interpreting, there are other types that should be briefly

mentioned in order to more clearly distinguish consecutive interpreting from the variety of other types. Recently, more and more attention is paid to this field of knowledge. I. Khaleeva considers linguodidactics to be a special branch of methodological science, which defines the essence of activity as a social phenomenon that grounds the content components of education, upbringing, education in an integral connection with the nature of language and the nature of communication. Linguistics is a methodological aspect of the theory of foreign language teaching. F.S. Abdullayeva defined the following directions of modern language didactics in the field of teaching foreign languages:

- the purpose of foreign language teaching;
- linguodidactics as a methodology of foreign language teaching;
- pragmalinguodidactics in teaching a foreign language;

F.S. Abdullayeva believes that "a foreign language can be learned only in accordance with the requirements of the specialty if there is a pragmatic foreign language competence and the ability to use it in professional activities." The integration of pragmatics, sociolinguistics and methodology, in turn, constitutes pragmalinguodidactics. Pragmalinguodidaktika studies the issues of teaching foreign language competence and international communication. Translation studies requires continuous research in the work of translators. Translation comes from the fact that it is a means of communication, because it is directly related to the interaction between languages and people. A native speaker of one language often cannot understand a speaker of another language due to a different perception of the world, differences in views formed over the centuries, which later affects mutual understanding. Translation is a complex, multifaceted and multifaceted activity, during which it is not only the conversion of one language into another, but also the interaction of different people, different mentalities, and cultures. At the same time, there is a clash of traditions, views and opinions. It is a valuable source of information about the languages involved in the translation process and the cultures to which these languages belong. In order to clarify and adequately understand the term "translation", its meaning should be disclosed as fully as possible, which allows to distinguish translation from other related and similar phenomena. The problem of defining the concept of "translation" is urgent and requires special attention, since there are different approaches to the interpretation of this term. In recent years, there has been an increased interest in the psychological approach to translation in general, and as a result, there has been a need to study the psycholinguistic aspect of consecutive translation. A methodology that has been used for many years in the field of consecutive translation has now been refined by recent research and hypotheses developed in the fields of psycholinguistics and the psychology of memory and attention. The views of scientists from different countries on the psycholinguistic processes occurring in the process of consecutive translation were comparatively analyzed. The stages of psycholinguistic perception of the text intended for translation are described, as well as the cognitive aspects of translation. Interpreting is an activity of great importance in the modern world of communication. The nature of commentary imposes certain limitations, such as time pressure, changing information, and the rapid selection of suitable topics to be covered in a short period of time. When studying the translation activity, it is necessary to clearly distinguish the types and methods of translation, because there are several methods that require learning along with

the two main types of translation - written and oral. The translator should emphasize the most important points of the speech, pay close attention to the tenses of the verbs, determine the relative importance of the secondary meaning elements and ignore the things that are not related to it. An analysis of the application of the competency-based approach to the training of consecutive translators was conducted. In addition to the existing competences of a serial translator, the need to develop another, namely reflexive competence, was identified. A serial interpreter must have a number of competencies to perform professional activities. Competences should be mastered in the process of translator training, and then formed and developed in each student. A distinction is also made between the concepts of ability and competence. There is a typology of texts aimed at translation. This typology also applies to PP. Also, a classification of texts different from the first one was developed. These classifications determine the need to study the linguistic features of texts belonging to a certain type. It is important to study the stages and mechanisms of consecutive translation in order to study the methodology of TS teaching in detail. Each step of the sequential interpreter, in turn, contains several things that are necessary for the operation of the interpreter. Mechanisms of sequential translation, including comprehension, italicization, and meaning transfer, have also been identified. The selected parameters serve as a basis for studying different aspects of the sequential interpretation process, as they help to differentiate meaning. It serves as a basis for the further development of effective strategies that can be used between interrelated models and in the educational process as well as in professional activities.

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